

Supplementary file

CD157 signaling promotes survival of acute myeloid leukemia cells and is a predictive marker of response to Mcl-1 inhibitors

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Table S1. Clinical and biological features of AML patients

Case #	Age	Sex	FAB classification	WHO classification	FLT3 ITD	NPM1 mut	Type of sample	Blasts (%)	Blasts CD157 ^{low} (%)	Blasts CD157 ^{dim} (%)	Blasts CD157 ^{high} (%)
1	57	F	M5b	Acute monocytic leukemia	-	+	PB	44	4	40	
2	50	M	M4	Acute myelomonocytic leukemia	+	-	BM	92		92	
3	38	M	M4	Acute myelomonocytic leukemia	-	-	BM	44		29	15
4	51	F	M4	Acute myelomonocytic leukemia	+	+	PB	93		93	
5	37	F	M4	Acute myelomonocytic leukemia	-	-	BM	85	32		53
6	52	F	NA	AML with recurrent genetic alterations	-	-	BM	43	34	9	
7	25	M	M4	Acute myelomonocytic leukemia	-	-	PB	36		27	9
8	50	F	M4	Acute myelomonocytic leukemia	+	+	BM	64		38	26
9	66	F	NA	AML with MDS	-	-	BM	53	53		
10	77	F	M4	Acute myelomonocytic leukemia	-	-	BM	85		85	
11	72	F	NA	NA	NA	NA	BM	79	55	24	
12	72	F	M2	AML with maturation	-	+	PB	70	70		
13	55	M	M1	AML with minimal maturation	-	-	PB	78	78		
14	68	F	M5	Acute monocytic leukemia	-	+	PB	47			47
15	47	F	M2	AML with maturation	-	-	PB	20	20		
16	77	F	M4	Acute myelomonocytic leukemia	-	-	PB	23	2		21
17	53	F	M4	Acute myelomonocytic leukemia	-	-	PB	76	10		66
18	69	F	M2	AML with maturation	+	+	PB	77	22	55	
19	86	M	NA	Secondary AML	-	-	PB	97	61	36	

FAB = French–American–British classification; WHO = World Health Organization classification; F = female; M = male; MDS = myelodysplastic syndrome; FLT3 = fms-like tyrosine kinase 3 gene; ITD = internal tandem duplication; NPM1 = nucleophosmin 1 gene; mut = mutated; NA = not available; PB = peripheral blood; BM = bone marrow.

CD157 Mean Fluorescence Intensity (MFI) ratio was calculated according to the formula (MFI of CD157 on blasts - MFI of CD157 on lymphocytes) / MFI of CD157 on lymphocytes.

CD157^{low} = MFI ratio <10; CD157^{dim} = MFI ratio ≥10 <50; CD157^{high} = MFI ratio ≥50

Figure S1. CD157 expression in primary AML cells assessed by multiparametric flow cytometry analysis. Leukemic blasts were identified as CD45^{dim} and SSC^{low}; specifically, myeloid blasts were CD33^{dim}, CD64⁻, CD117⁺, CD123⁺, HLA-DR⁺. Immature monocytic populations were CD33⁺, CD64⁺⁺, CD117^{low/neg}, CD123⁺, HLA-DR⁺⁺. CD157-MFI ratio was calculated according to the formula: (CD157 MFI on blasts – CD157 MFI on lymphocytes)/CD157 MFI on lymphocytes. (a) CD157 expression on leukemic myeloid blasts and leukemic monocytic populations in each patient. Blue dotted lines indicate the CD157 MFI ratio used as cutoff: CD157^{low} = MFI ratio <10; CD157^{dim} = MFI ratio ≥10 <50; CD157^{high} = MFI ratio ≥50. (b) Comparison of CD157 expression in leukemic myeloid blasts versus leukemic monocytic populations. CD157 expression was significantly higher on leukemic monocytic populations than on leukemic myeloid blasts ($p < 0.0001$, Mann-Whitney test). (c) Representative FACS plot of CD157 expression in bone marrow (pt #2, pt #3 and pt #10) or peripheral blood (pt #4) from patients with AML used for functional experiments showed in Figure 1. After excluding doublets and debris, blasts and lymphocytes were selected based on their SSC and CD45 expression profiles. CD117 expression was used to further characterize blast populations.

Figure S2. CD157 expression in AML cell lines. (a) U937 and THP1 cells were stably transduced with two CD157-specific shRNA (shCD157#1, shCD157#2) or a scrambled shRNA (CD157control). (b) OCI-AML3 cell were stably transduced with CD157-specific shRNA #1. CD157 mRNA (a, b) and protein expression (c) were analysed by RT-PCR and flow cytometry, respectively. β -actin and an isotype matched mAb (gray peaks) were used as controls, respectively. (d) Proliferation of U937, THP1 and OCI-AML3 AML cell lines engineered for the expression of CD157. Results are expressed as fold increase compared to time zero and are the mean \pm SEM of three independent experiments performed in quadruplicate.

Figure S3. Effect of ABT199 on U937 cell viability. (a) CD157-high (red line) or CD157-low (green line) U937 cells were exposed to increasing concentration of ABT-199 for 24 h before analysis of cell viability using Presto Blue assays. Data represents the percentage of live cells compared to control cells treated with vehicle. Results are the mean \pm SEM of three experiments performed in triplicate. (b) CD157-high (white bars) or low (grey bars) U937 cells were treated with vehicle or with AraC (10 μ M) and ABT199 (0.5 μ M) as single agents or in combination for 24 h, then were subjected to AnnexinV/PI staining and flow cytometry analysis. Bars represent the percentage of AnnexinV-negative/PI-negative cells. Results are the mean \pm SEM of three independent experiments.

Figure S4. Effect of S63845 and AraC combination on U937 cell viability. U937/CD157high or U937/CD157low cells were treated with AraC (10 μ M) and S63845 (20 nM) as single agents or in combination for 24 h, then were subjected to AnnexinV/PI staining and flow cytometry analysis. Bars represent the percentage of AnnexinV-negative/PI-negative cells. Results are the mean \pm SEM of eleven independent experiments.